

Youth Goals

Research Centre

JEAN MONNET MODULE

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Report

Academic Conferences I, II and III

Salamanca
University of Salamanca

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1st and 2nd Academic Day

Mauricio Bitrán

20/02/2024-22/02/2024

OVERVIEW

The academic sessions on the use of scientific evidence in public policy development, given by Maurice Bitran, PhD (Munk School of Global Affairs and Public Policy, University of Toronto), were conceived as a space for reflection and learning about the importance of science, statistics and epidemiology for the formulation of effective government initiatives. These sessions brought together students, professors, researchers and practitioners from a variety of fields to promote the adoption of rigorous methods in policy design and evaluation.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the event were as follows:

- To disseminate the value of scientific evidence in the field of public policy, especially in areas such as public health, occupational health and environmental protection.
- Explain the types of scientific studies (in vitro, in vivo, in silico and human), highlighting their advantages, limitations and relevance to different research contexts.
- To teach how to critically assess the quality of studies through the analysis of random errors, biases and confounding factors, as well as peer review and the importance of sound methodological design.
- To highlight the role of social acceptability in the effectiveness of policies, inviting reflection on the relationship between Science, Policy and Society.

AGENDA

The programme of the academic days was as follows:

Presentation of the event and objectives of the session
Presentation by the rapporteur: Maurice Bitrán
Master Exhibition
Dialogue of the speaker with the participants
Conclusions, satisfaction surveys and closure

EVENT

Presentation of the conference and objectives of the session

- Introduction to the importance of integrating scientific evidence into government decision-making.
- Brief overview of the speaker and his main contributions in the field of evidence-based policy making.

Sources and types of scientific information

- Peer-reviewed journals, grey literature and conference proceedings.
- Distinction between in vitro, in vivo, in silico and human studies, with examples of public policy applications.

Design and critical evaluation of scientific studies

- Review of epidemiological methods: cohorts, case-control, cross-sectional studies and randomised clinical trials.
- Analysis of random and systematic errors, confounding factors, and how to reduce them through rigorous experimental designs.

Other considerations in public policy development

- The relevance of social acceptability and the need to build trust in science and institutions.
- Discussion on the importance of collaboration between the scientific community, political actors and citizens for effective policy making.

Conclusions and closure

- Synthesis of the main lessons learned and reflections.
- Invitation to continue to explore and apply good practice in evidence-based policy making and evaluation.

3rd Academic Day

Bringing the National Statistics Institute closer to Society

27/11/2024

OVERVIEW

The conference focused on the relevance of data in society and the role played by the National Statistics Institute (INE). It also addressed the professional experiences of speakers with consolidated careers and new recruits, which allowed them to learn not only about the main functions of the INE, but also about the professional development opportunities it offers.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the event were as follows:

- To disseminate the work and impact of INE in the production of official statistics.
- Discuss the importance of data today, both for citizens and for public administration.
- Share professional experiences on access and career paths within INE, highlighting the competencies required to perform their duties.
- Promote dialogue on data analysis and its contribution to decision-making.

AGENDA

The programme of the academic day was as follows:

Presentation of the event and objectives of the session
Presentation of the speakers: Cristóbal José Rojas, Julio César Hernández, Cristina Ramos, Alejandro Rodríguez and Silvia Blanco.
Round Table: The Importance of Data and the Role of INE in Society
Testimonials from new recruits
From Data to Decision: Short-term Statistics in Today's Economy
Question and Answer Session
Conclusions, satisfaction survey and closure

EVENT

Opening of the conference

Welcome and introduction by YGRC project researchers, emphasising the close links between INE and society.

Round Table: The Importance of Data and the Role of INE in Society

- **Cristóbal José Rojas:** INE's mission, history and objectives, together with concrete examples of how its statistics affect everyday life.
- **Julio César Hernández:** Access to state bodies, competition process and main contributions to the work carried out by INE.

Testimonials from new recruits

- **Cristina Ramos:** An account of her transition from university to joining INE, her expectations and possible contributions.
- **Alejandro Rodríguez:** Description of the preparation process and motivations for joining INE, as well as his first impressions of the institution.

From Data to Decision: Short-term Statistics in Today's Economy

- **Silvia Blanco Poveda:** Professional career, most significant projects and recommendations for future professionals interested in statistics.

Question and Answer Session

A space where attendees could ask questions and make comments to the speakers, generating a dialogue on the value of data and the role of the INE.

The day combined keynote presentations with a roundtable format and personal testimonies, which provided a comprehensive overview of INE's activity and its usefulness in different sectors. It was attended by university students, teachers, researchers and professionals from different areas interested in the impact of statistics on public policy-making and resource management.

The diversity of perspectives allowed for an enriching debate on the importance of reliable data and the role of youth in the modernisation of information collection and analysis systems. The day concluded by underlining the relevance of transparency and statistical culture in building a more informed and efficient future.

QUALITY ASSESSMENT

The evaluation of the cycle of Academic Days of the European Youth Policies and Youth Goals Programme has combined qualitative and quantitative methodological approaches, strategically selected according to the nature and format of each day.

The first two days were held in a smaller and more interactive format, with groups of between 30 and 50 people, which allowed for a climate of trust and proximity to be generated. In this context, we opted for a qualitative evaluation based on constructive dialogue and participatory observation. At the end of each session, open conversations were held with the participants, in which valuable impressions were gathered on the content, dynamics and impact of the event.

Among the aspects most highlighted by the participants are the following:

- The high interest and practical usefulness of the contents covered.
- The connection with previous theoretical knowledge acquired in their training courses.
- The proximity and accessibility of the speakers, facilitating a horizontal exchange in an environment of trust.
- The relevance of the close and participatory format, which encouraged a deeper reflection on the relationship between science, society and politics.

This qualitative approach made it possible to capture complex perceptions, emotions and meaningful interactions, enriching the evaluation from a human and pedagogical dimension.

The third day, organised in collaboration with the National Statistics Institute (INE), brought together more than 100 attendees, which led to the implementation of a structured quantitative evaluation through questionnaires. The results of this evaluation reflected a broadly positive assessment, with average scores above 4 out of 5 in all the indicators analysed, as well as a generalised perception of learning, usefulness and satisfaction with the activity.

During the event, a first questionnaire was carried out with the aim of gathering initial information about the attendees, including data such as country of origin, organisation of origin, previous experience in similar events and their current situation.

The majority of participants (94%) were from Spain. However, there was also a strong international presence, with participants from Latin American countries such as Venezuela, Argentina, Honduras, Chile, Colombia and Mexico, as well as from the United States. The University of Salamanca was the most represented institution, although members of the Guardia Civil and the Castilla y León Ministry of Health also participated.

In terms of previous experience, 50 % had previously attended activities related to the topic, while for the other half it was their first participation. Regarding their current situation, were studying at the University of Salamanca, although there were also people in active employment.

At the end of the day, attendees were asked to complete a satisfaction questionnaire. The main results are detailed below.

Overall satisfaction with the activity was assessed on a scale of 1 to 5 stars, with 1 indicating a very low rating and 5 indicating a very high rating. The result was very positive, with an average score of 4.1, and with the majority of responses concentrated in the highest values (4 and 5 stars) (Figure 1). Also noteworthy was the perception of improvement in the knowledge acquired, with an average score of 4.2, with the highest scores again being the most frequent (Figure 2). These results reflect a very favourable overall assessment by the participants.

Figure1 : Attendees' overall satisfaction with the activity

Figure2 : Perception of knowledge improvement after the workshop

When respondents were asked about the importance of data and information for society (Figure 3), all answers were in the top levels of the scale, between "quite a lot" and "very much", with the latter being the most selected option (63.3%).

Regarding the role of statistics in everyday life (Figure 4), 57.1% considered it "very important", 34.7% "quite important" and only 8. rated it as "somewhat important", showing a mostly positive perception.

Figure3 : Perception of the importance of data for society

Figure4 : Assessment of the importance of statistics in everyday life

The organisation of the event was well rated (Figure 5), with an average score of 4.16 out of 5. Likewise, satisfaction with the information received and shared during the day reached an average of 4.1, which reinforces the generally good reception by the public (Figure 6).

Figure5 : Opinion on the organisation of the event

Figure6 : Satisfaction with information received and shared

The selection of speakers was rated very positively by attendees (Figure 7): 42.9% rated it as "very interesting" and 40.8% as "quite interesting", reflecting a high degree of satisfaction with the quality and relevance of the presentations.

In addition, participants were given the possibility to indicate which part of the event they found most useful or interesting, and could select one or more options (Figure 8). The most highly rated part was Part 2: Testimonials from new recruits, which received 35 votes. It was followed by Part 1: Importance of data, the role of INE in society and opposition processes, with 27 votes. Finally, Part 3: My experience at INE received 11 votes.

These results show the interest generated, especially by the personal testimonies, and provide valuable information for the design of future activities.

Figure7 : Interest generated by the selection of speakers

Figure8 : Part of the event that was most useful or interesting

The average rating on whether the day met attendees' expectations was 3.98 out of 5, a high score and close to the maximum value, indicating a satisfactory experience for the majority (Figure 9).

As a further indicator of the positive impact of the event, 94% of participants stated that they would recommend this type of activity to others, reinforcing the perceived usefulness and quality of the event.

Figure9 : Rating of whether the event met expectations

Overall, the results of the questionnaire reflect a very positive reception by the students, highlighting the interest in the contents, the perception of real learning and the organisational quality of the day. The average score for all the items evaluated was above 4 out of 5, which shows a high level of general satisfaction.

Particularly relevant are the high ratings in aspects such as the improvement of knowledge, the perception of the role of statistics in everyday life and the importance of data for society. All this points to a receptive and committed attitude on the part of the university public to proposals that link science, citizenship and public institutions such as the INE.

Although the lowest scores were minimal, it is worth taking into account those who felt that the event did not fully meet their expectations. This minority group can offer valuable clues for future editions, such as adapting the contents to different profiles or expanding the spaces for direct participation.

This combination of approaches - qualitative in the first sessions and quantitative in the last one - has made it possible to comprehensively capture the formative and experiential impact of the workshops. Through this mixed evaluation, it has been possible to confirm that the programme has offered significant learning spaces, where active participation, critical thinking and the link between youth, public policies and data for decision-making are promoted.

CONCLUSIONS

These data reinforce the idea that initiatives such as this one generate impact, contribute to a greater understanding of the role of data in society, and consolidate the link between public institutions and university youth from an educational and civic perspective. The results obtained support the continuity of this type of activities and suggest the possibility of extending them to new audiences.

The combination of theoretical training, personal testimonies and participatory spaces has proven to be effective in bringing the role of data, statistics and public institutions closer to university youth. Moreover, the mixed methodological approach used - qualitative on the first two days and quantitative on the third day - allowed us to capture the training experience in greater depth from different perspectives.

While the first sessions favoured direct dialogue in small groups, allowing for a closer and more horizontal exchange, the third day made it possible to obtain systematic and quantifiable data that show a high degree of satisfaction, learning and motivation on the part of the students.

Overall, the cycle of conferences has fulfilled its objective of fostering a critical and participatory scientific culture, strengthening the skills of young people in the analysis of public policies and the use of evidence for decision-making. Likewise, the value of this type of meeting to strengthen ties between the university, public institutions and young citizens has been confirmed, laying the foundations for future collaborations and training activities along these lines.

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